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6 A time-resolved single-cell roadmap of the logic driving anterior neural crest 7 diversification from neural border to migration stages

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27 Significance statement

28 The neural crest cells (NCC), a highly multipotent vertebrate-specific population induced in the gastrula
29 ectoderm, emerges by an epithelial-mesenchymal-transition (EMT) in late neurulas. NCC induction and
30 diversification prior to EMT remains only partially explored. Using single-cell transcriptomes with fine
31 temporal resolution, machine learning, and experimental validation in *Xenopus*, we here provide the first
32 global scaffold of the gene programs driving anterior NCC induction during gastrulation and its
33 diversification during neurulation. Importantly, we select two key transcription factors and use high-
34 throughput strategies (RNAseq and ChIPseq on dissected ectoderm tissue) to validate their connectomes

35 and actions in gene program switches predicted *in silico*. This allowed us to propose a new architecture
36 for transcriptome regulations driving premigratory NCC formation.

37 **Abstract**

38 Neural crest cells exemplify cellular diversification from a multipotent progenitor population.
39 However, the full sequence of early molecular choices orchestrating the emergence of neural crest
40 heterogeneity from the embryonic ectoderm remains elusive. Gene-regulatory-networks (GRN) govern
41 early development and cell specification towards definitive neural crest. Here, we combine ultra-dense
42 single cell transcriptomes with machine-learning and large-scale transcriptomic and epigenomic
43 experimental validation of selected trajectories, to provide the general principles and highlight specific
44 features of the GRN underlying neural crest fate diversification from induction to early migration stages
45 using *Xenopus* frog embryos as a model. During gastrulation, a transient neural border zone state precedes
46 the choice between neural crest and placodes which includes multiple converging gene programs. During
47 neurulation, transcription factor connectome and bifurcation analyses demonstrate the early emergence of
48 neural crest fates at the neural plate stage, alongside an unbiased multipotent-like lineage persisting until
49 epithelial-mesenchymal transition stage. We also decipher circuits driving cranial and vagal neural crest
50 formation and provide a broadly applicable high-throughput validation strategy for investigating single
51 cell transcriptomes in vertebrate GRNs in development, evolution, and disease.

52

53 **Introduction**

54 Neural crest cells form a population of multipotent and migratory progenitors found in vertebrate
55 embryos, essential for the peripheral and enteric nervous system, craniofacial structures, endocrine and
56 pigment cells among others. Together with ectodermal placodes, neural crest (NC) cells are evolutionary
57 inventions that support many cell and tissue innovations promoting the vertebrate predatory lifestyle.
58 Shortly after gastrulation, NC cells are induced from the dorsal-lateral "neural border zone" (NB), an
59 ectoderm domain located between the non-neural ectoderm and the neural plate ectoderm (1, 2). In
60 addition to the NC, the NB territory also gives rise to posterior placodes, non-neural ectoderm and the
61 dorsal part of the neural tube (3, 4). Whether these four cell types arise from a common and multipotent
62 early progenitor state, and how the sequence of fate decisions is orchestrated at the NB during gastrulation
63 remain open questions. During neurulation, NC specification and induction progresses as an anterior-to-
64 posterior wave along the edges of the neural plate, with gene programs that define early and immature
65 neural crest cells (e.g. expression of *snail2*, *foxd3* and *sox8* genes) followed by later pre-migratory
66 programs presaging emigration of NC cells from the NB epithelium as the neural folds elevate and close
67 (e.g. expression of *sox10*, *twist1* and *cdh2* (*N-cadherin*) genes) (5, 6). In addition to this pan-NC program,

68 several regional molecular modules are activated along the anterior-posterior body axis and define
69 subpopulations with specific potential (7, 8). How these programs are interconnected with the pan-NC
70 module, and how and when they are activated in pre-migratory NC cells is poorly described. Later, at the
71 end of neurulation, NC cells leave the dorsal ectoderm by a stereotypical epithelium-to-mesenchymal
72 transition (EMT) followed by extensive migration towards a variety of target tissues.

73 NC biology has been scrutinized during development and evolution, leading to the elucidation of
74 elaborate gene regulatory networks (GRNs) during the last decade (9–12). These networks, however,
75 remain incomplete and do not account for most of the defects observed in human neurocristopathies (13,
76 14). This problem is ripe for single cell (SC) transcriptomics, which would enable a full description of NC
77 development over sequential developmental stages, and which would define the developmental genetic
78 trajectories of the complete NC lineage tree, compared to progenitor cell states at the neural border. Many
79 recent SC studies on NC cells have explored NC after emigration (Table S1). In contrast, premigratory
80 NC single cells and the links with earlier ectoderm patterning have received very limited exploration and
81 validation (7, 15, 16). Previously, formation of the NB territory has been defined by the relatively specific
82 expression of a few genes during gastrulation (e.g. *pax3* and *pax7*) and by the overlapping expression of
83 ventral (*tfap2a*, *msx1*) and dorsal (*zic1*) genes (2, 9, 17). However, whether NB represents a distinct cell
84 state, the timing of its specification from the rest of the dorsal ectoderm and the circuits driving fate
85 decisions between the four NB-derived cell fates (NC, placodes, non-neural ectoderm and dorsal neural
86 tube) remain to be established (3, 18, 19). Furthermore, the subsequent timing of lineage decisions in the
87 pre-migratory NC along the anterior-posterior axis, the potential long-term maintenance of a multipotent
88 NC subpopulation, and the molecular mechanisms driving each state of the premigratory NC lineage
89 remain mostly unexplored. Here, we used single cell transcriptomes from eight consecutive developmental
90 stages of *Xenopus tropicalis*, featuring 6135 NC cells and 17138 early ectoderm cells, to provide a
91 comprehensive developmental profiling of the NB and the pre-migratory NC. During neurulation, we
92 define sixteen NC subpopulations and highlight the transcriptomic trajectories between ‘early’
93 premigratory NC states and ‘late’ NC subpopulations emigrating from cranial to vagal levels of the body
94 axis. Interestingly, we find that distinct signatures for prospective NC fates emerge much earlier than
95 previously anticipated, that NC state diversity is maintained upon EMT, contrasting with reports in mouse
96 cranial NC (15), and that further diversification occurs at the onset of migration. We then connect
97 ectoderm patterning during gastrulation to NC and placodes specification. Interestingly, rather than
98 individual clusters, we find a series of transitional clusters supported by distinct molecular trajectory
99 predictions. At each stage, we propose a temporal sequence of molecular events underlying these

100 successive transcriptomic states and identify key candidate transcription factors for the branching between
101 states. Importantly, we validate selected regulatory predictions using transcriptomes of dissected NB or
102 NC explants, transcription factor binding to chromatin (TF-ChIP-seq) and *in vivo* approaches, supporting
103 the pertinence of in-silico predictions. Last, we propose a model of “dual convergence” for parallel
104 transcriptomic routes driving neural border specification and a “diversification tree” for premigratory NC.
105 Altogether, we provide an extensive gene regulatory network describing the emergence of the neural crest
106 from the ectoderm of vertebrate embryos.

107

108 **Results**

109 **Defining the diversity of premigratory neural crest states.**

110 We used the single-cell (SC) series from Briggs et al., 2018 (20) and performed deeper re-
111 sequencing of the libraries from whole *X. tropicalis* embryos taken at 8 consecutive developmental stages,
112 followed by updated genome annotation and improved sequence alignment. The quality of the new dataset
113 is compared to previous NC datasets in other species (data processing is described in Materials and
114 Methods and Supplementary Information (S.I.) Part B and S.I. Table S1). Through unsupervised Leiden
115 clustering (21) of the whole embryo dataset at each stage (a total of 177250 cells), we identified NC
116 clusters by co-expression of well-established NC genes, such as *snai2*, *TFAP2B*, and *SOXE* genes, from
117 induction to migration (gene-supervised approach, Fig. 1A-B; Fig. S1A; S.I. Table S2). This allowed us
118 to scrutinize 6135 neural crest (NC) cells from early gastrulation to early migration stages. The large cell
119 number of our new dataset allowed greater assessment of the cellular diversity in the NC population during
120 early induction (at late gastrulation stages 12-13 and neural plate stages 13-14), during neural fold
121 elevation (stages 16-18), during EMT (neural tube stages 18-20) and at the earliest stages of NC cells
122 emigration (tailbud stage 22). To validate the gene-supervised approach used to define NC cells,
123 signatures of NC/non-NC cells from the whole annotated frog dataset were then used to train a classifier
124 which could faithfully detect NC cells when applied to an independent and poorly related zebrafish whole
125 embryo dataset (22). This test indicated that the initial gene-supervised selection had retrieved *bona fide*
126 NC cells (S.I. Part B; Fig. S1B-E). We then used the NC dataset (and not the whole embryo dataset as
127 above) to define which genes would best characterize the NC cell population compared to other embryonic
128 cells at each developmental stage: an ideal pan-NC marker can be defined based on its highly NC-specific
129 expression compared to non-NC cells, and low variation in expression across the NC population (Fig. 1C).
130 This highlighted that the early NC is best labeled by *snai2* at stages 13-16, followed by *tfap2b* from stage

131 14 to 20, and *c3*, *c9*, *sox8* between stages 14 to 18. Comparatively among these genes, *tfap2b* was the
132 most specific NC marker, albeit not strictly exclusive as pronephros and other cells express *tfap2b* at
133 tailbud stages (S.I. Part A). However, collectively, these genes thus define an early and generic "pan-NC"
134 signature.

135 We then explored diversity of the premigratory NC cells population, and if transitional states could
136 be identified during neurulation (Fig. 2 and S2). From late gastrulation to emigration stages, we defined
137 16 different NC states (c1 to c16), compared to the 8 described previously (20) (Fig. 2A). All NC cells
138 expressed the generic "pan-NC" signature (Fig. 2B), either alone (c5, c14, thereafter called "unbiased"
139 clusters) or in combination with other markers (Fig. 2B-D). Partition-based graph abstraction analysis
140 (PAGA) (23) showed that most NC clusters were highly interconnected with stronger connectivity within
141 early (c1-c4), vagal (c8, c9, c12 and c13), and cranial (c10, c7 and c11) clusters (Fig. 2E). The clusters
142 could be identified based on unique combinations of marker gene expressions, although subsets of these
143 markers were shared between closely related clusters, particularly those containing cell states transitioning
144 from one to another (such as *mafb*⁺ vagal c9 and c12, Fig. 2C and D). Further clustering lost significance
145 as the resulting sub-clusters expressed similar marker gene expression. Each cluster's gene signature and
146 proposed biological characteristics are detailed in S.I. Part A and S.I. Table S3. We thus only highlight
147 here a few interesting features of this premigratory/early migrating NC dataset. First, we have identified
148 11 clusters (c6-c16), composed mainly of stage 18-22 cells, with an explicit mesenchymal NC signature,
149 *i.e.*, various levels of *itga4*/integrin- α 4, *vim*/vimentin or *fn1*/fibronectin (Fig. S2B). This indicated that
150 those cells were preparing or engaging EMT and early migration, thus provided the opportunity to explore
151 gene expression dynamics and other molecular characteristics of EMT *in vivo*. For example, we compared
152 EMT in cranial and vagal NC, using *hox* gene signatures to position each cluster along the body axis:
153 cranial-most clusters were *hox*-negative while vagal clusters expressed a range of anterior
154 (rhombencephalon, *hoxa-d 1-3*) to posterior (spinal cord, *hoxa-d 7-11*) *hox* genes (Fig. S2C). With this
155 knowledge of distinct spatial positions spanning cranial to vagal NC, we queried whether all NC cells
156 adopted a similar "stem-like" state upon EMT as proposed recently in the mouse (15). Instead, we
157 observed clear transcriptomic diversity across the mesenchymal clusters: for example, c10, c13 and c15
158 all undergo a transition to a mesenchymal *vim*⁺ state but c10 and c15 expressed the ectomesodermal
159 marker *twi1*, while c13 highly expressed *tnc* (Fig. 2D and S3). Moreover, there has been a debate in the
160 field, especially in trunk NC, about the appearance of lineage-specific markers prior to EMT (24–26). As
161 one key expectation from SC transcriptomics is to identify and characterize novel rare cell states, we

162 specifically searched for NC lineage determination markers in premigratory cranial and vagal NC. We
163 found no sign of cell determination towards the melanoblast, neural or glial lineage. Instead, we clearly
164 identified clusters enriched in markers essential for NC cell migration (semaphorin co-receptors *nrp1* in
165 c12 and c15, and *nrp2* in c10 and c11). Shortly after EMT, we also found a few cells enriched myogenic
166 cell markers expression (*actc1*, *myl*, *mylpf*, *des*) in c16, along with *tfap2b*, *sox10*, *twil*, *mmp14* expression
167 (Fig. 2D, S2). The identity of this small population remains unclear, as discussed in S.I. Part A. This
168 finding aligns with recent cranial NC lineage tracing which indicates that the majority of NC cell fates are
169 established after EMT (26–29).

170 This dataset's main asset is that it follows NC cell states over a large developmental time series
171 spanning gastrulation to EMT. We looked how the emigrating cell states were related to induction-stage
172 states, in order to define the potential trajectories underlying NC early diversification. Through PAGA,
173 we observed the relationships between clusters and were able to define multiple progenitor states linked
174 to the later clusters defined above. Consequently, we delineated transcriptional dynamics of cranial, vagal
175 and enteric nervous system progenitors between late gastrulation and EMT. These clusters mainly include
176 cells from late gastrula (st12) to mid-neurula (st16) stages. Late cranial c10 (*nrp2⁺rpe65⁺hox⁻*) and c11
177 (*nrp2⁺dlx2⁺hox⁻*) were related to c7 (*nrp2⁺ hox⁻*) while late vagal c12 (*maf^{b+}epha4⁺*) and c13
178 (*tnc⁺wnt11⁺ltbp1⁺*) were linked to c9 (*nrp1⁺*). C13 was also linked to the early c3 (*hnf1b⁺*) indicating a
179 possible converging trajectory. In turn, c7 and c9 were related to the unbiased c5 (*tfap2c⁺sox9⁺*). The *nrp1⁺*
180 late cranial c15 was linked to c6 and c4, all of which specifically expressed *cyp26c1*, *epha2* and *efnb2*.
181 C16 (*myl1⁺*, Fig. S4) was related to unbiased c14, which was in turn linked to unbiased c5, c1 (*c9⁺sox9⁺*)
182 and c2 (*gjb1⁺*) (Fig. S5, S6 and S7). Several genes found enriched in each progenitor cluster were
183 consistent with previous experimental analyses, validating our SC-transcriptome-based predictions (see
184 detailed description in S.I. Part A). This analysis allowed defining potential progenitor state larger
185 signatures compared to previous *in vivo* experiments and selecting the clusters pertinent for further
186 trajectory analysis (see below).

187 Interestingly, most clusters gathered cells from multiple stages, indicating that a given
188 transcriptome state can be reached by different cells over long developmental periods (Fig. S3). For
189 example, cranialmost cells of c10 are generated over the entire duration of neurulation from neural plate
190 stage 13 to migration stage 22. This reflects how NC cells of a similar state can be continuously generated
191 over the course of development at a given portion of the neuraxis. In contrast, cranial c11 and c15, two
192 migratory clusters highly expressing *vimentin* (*vim⁺*), are suddenly generated at post-EMT stage 22. This

193 could reflect an abrupt step of mesenchymalisation in the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition process of
194 cranial NC, as reflected in their transcriptomes.

195 Last, we also detected cells with an immature pan-NC signature throughout neurulation and EMT,
196 representing a long-lasting, potentially “multipotent” and “stem-like” population (c1, c5, c14; Fig. 3).
197 These “unbiased” progenitors formed 72% of all NC cells during induction (gastrula and neural plate
198 stages 12-14), 15% at pre-migratory and EMT stages 16-18, and 9% among tailbud stage 22 NC cells
199 (Fig. S2D-E). Compared to c1-c5, we find that c14 cells express medium levels of pluripotency markers
200 *sox2*, *cmyc* and *pou5f3.1*, along with pan-NC markers. As c14 is formed of cells from stages 13 to 22 (Fig.
201 S3), we detail that this expression is found not only in the early (stages 13-16) cells but also the later ones
202 (stages 18-22, Fig. 3A-B). This is compared to higher levels in early “unbiased” clusters c1-c5 and lower
203 levels in c11 and c15 taken as examples of biased ones. We confirmed *pou5f3.1* expression by *in situ*
204 hybridization in NC explants until the end of neurulation (stage 18). Last, c14 cells express *mmp14*
205 suggesting engagement in the EMT process (Fig.S2). This suggests that a small population of naïve NC
206 cells may be maintained as highly plastic throughout neurulation and NC EMT. Further functional studies,
207 including lineage tracing, are needed to define the potential of these cells *in vivo*.

208 In summary, with its large cell number and temporal series, our data details the continuum of NC
209 states along a large segment of the body axis, from the anteriormost cranial to the vagal levels. We
210 highlight three main novel points characterizing NC cells around the time of induction to initiation of
211 migration. Firstly, there is a large diversity of cell states along the cranio-caudal axis throughout this
212 developmental period, including spatially-defined cell groups (regional modules), transitional states and
213 multipotent-like cells. Secondly, state diversity is maintained across stages including during EMT, with
214 cells of different developmental time presenting similar transcriptome states. Lastly, a small ‘stem-like’
215 unbiased NC subpopulation persists as a distinct cluster until EMT.

216 **Connectome analysis by intersecting SC-transcriptomics modelling with *in vivo* morpholino RNA-** 217 **seq and transcription-factor-based ChIP-seq.**

218 To expand the network of genes involved in the NC-GRN, we used an input list of 1417
219 transcription factors (TFs) (30) and applied GRNboost2 on the NC dataset to link transcription factors to
220 their potential targets in the NC transcriptome. The principle of GRNBoost2 relies on analysis of gene
221 synexpression dynamics (31). We retrieved a vast network of 16978 potential TF-targets with a median
222 of 22 connections per TF. Among the most connected genes for each stage (S.I. Table S4), we retrieved

223 the previously known neural border specifiers *pax3* and *zic1* at NC induction stages, as well as *zic3*, *olig4*,
224 *sox9* and the anterior NC marker *dmx1*. At pre-migratory stages, the prominent nodes included the NC
225 specifiers *tfap2b*, *sox10* and *snai2*, the anterior NC markers *rpe65* and *alx1*, and the hindbrain hox gene
226 *hoxb3*. At migration stages, *tfap2e*, *mycn*, *dlx2* and *egr2* (*krox20*) displayed both high expression and
227 multiple connections.

228 To confront the predicted network to experimental data obtained *in vivo*, we chose two well-known
229 regulators of NC induction, Pax3 (9, 32) and TFAP2e (33) also identified as major nodes by GRNBoost2.
230 We sequenced microdissected NB/NC explants after *in vivo* knockdown of either *pax3* or *tfap2e*, using
231 previously validated antisense morpholino oligonucleotides (MO) (Fig. 4A,E). Expression was decreased
232 for 1179 transcripts in Pax3 morphant explants, confirming that Pax3 is essential for NB/NC development
233 (*zic1*, *msx1*, *msx2*, *sox9*) and identifying a large series of novel targets (*olig4*, *hnf1b*, *vim*, *olfm4*, *dhrs3*)
234 (Fig. 4A, Table S6). We also identified genes putatively directly bound by Pax3 *in vivo* using ChIP-seq
235 (Fig. 4B and 4C) and identified 657 potential targets in the whole stage 14 embryo, of which we selected
236 the 475 were expressed in the SC NC dataset (Table S8), including known direct targets, *e.g.* *cxcr4* and
237 *prtg* (2, 34) and novel potential ones (*e.g.* *efna3* and *psen2*) (Fig. 4C and S8). In contrast to the previously
238 known role of TFAP2e in NC induction (33), GRNBoost2 identified TFAP2e as a major node later on, at
239 neural fold stage. We thus used a similar approach on NC explants at a later stage (stages 17-19) and
240 validated TFAP2e as an important regulator of NC EMT markers, decreased expression of 586 genes
241 including *twist1*, *sox10*, *sncaip* and *fn1* (Fig. 4E; Table S7). Using ChIP-seq for TFAP2e, we identified
242 642 potential targets expressed in the NC dataset, among 805 potential targets for the whole stage 19
243 embryo, including top-scored *rbm20*, *pim1*, *adam33* and *tfap2a* (Fig. 4F and S4; Table S9). Controls for
244 these ChIP experiments are presented in Fig. S4. By themselves, these validation datasets based on
245 microdissected morphant samples and transcription-factor-based ChIPseq provide two new genome-wide
246 NC-GRNs centered on Pax3 and TFAP2e respectively, ready for later functional exploration.

247 We then compared these *in vivo* data to GRNBoost2 predictions. Due to their use of different
248 parameters (*e.g.* putative target gene binding by ChIP, direct and indirect regulation by knock-down,
249 stage-wise gene expression levels for synexpression, etc.) we expected to find only a partial overlap
250 between the potential target genes identified by each method. However, we also wondered if crossing
251 those approaches would highlight common, potential targets to prioritize in follow-up studies. We thus
252 explored gene list intersections in each case. For example, among 848 putative targets of TFAP2e
253 predicted from scRNA-seq, 99 showed changed expression after TFAP2e knockdown in NC explants *in*

254 *vivo* (e.g., *tfap2b*, *sox10*, *sncap*, *zic3*; Fig. S4), while 80 of the Pax3 ChIPseq-validated potential targets
255 were predicted by GRN-Boost2 modelling including *psmd4*, *psen2*, *sp7*, *notch1* and *hnf1b*. In both Pax3
256 and TFAP2e cases, we find that the three approaches partially overlap, identifying 17 and 20 candidate
257 gene targets for Pax3 and Tfp2e respectively, validated through all 3 techniques. To compare these results
258 to a random chance we utilized bootstrapping. To do this, we randomly selected the same number of genes
259 for different methods (ChIP-seq, MO, GRNboost2) 1000 times from the total number of genes (*X.laevis*
260 and *X.tropicalis*). We obtained a median intersection value of 3, confirming that our analyses were not
261 obtained at random and that we obtained a statistical enrichment (Fig. 4D, 4G and S4H), which encourages
262 special future focus on those genes.

263 **Branching towards biased premigratory neural crest subpopulations is controlled by key**
264 **transcription factors.**

265 To explore the temporal dynamics of TF expression that may specify decision points in the
266 development of pre-migratory NC, we used tree inference (ELPiGraph) and advanced pseudotime
267 downstream analysis focused on fate biasing using scFates (35, 36). We thus explored potential branch-
268 specific transcriptional regulation from the calculated pseudotime, in order to determine not only the
269 temporal order in which their functions may be accomplished but also genes which may bias the NC
270 towards a fate. EIPiGraph approximates datasets with complex topologies to build the graph structure,
271 with the limitation that it cannot be applied to large datasets with many potential branches. Thus, using
272 the principal graph constructed with PAGA (Fig. 2B), we sub-selected cells around three main bifurcation
273 points in the NC lineage tree and then applied scFates branching analysis (Fig. 5).

274 ***Cranial versus vagal bifurcation at the end of neural plate stage.***

275 Cranial NC cells emerge from the neural tube anterior to the otic vesicle while vagal NC cells form
276 from the hindbrain region adjacent to somites 1–7 (37). Our data indicated that the first cells biased
277 towards vagal or cranial populations arose from the unbiased cluster c5 around early neural fold stage 14.
278 Although we did not see a separation of c5 into two populations at the chosen level of clustering, we still
279 observe an early internal bias marked by the increased expression of early cranial (*nrp2*) and vagal (*mafb*)
280 markers in distinct sub-regions of c5: c5 cells that highly express *nrp2* were 7 times closer to the cranial
281 state, while cells that highly express *mafb* were 1.5 times closer to the vagal state (Fig. S5). Through
282 branching analysis, we uncovered gene programs potentially governing the bifurcation, consisting of

283 ‘early’ genes activated before bifurcation and ‘late’ genes with continued expression in each branch: *nrp2*,
284 *alk*, *rnd1*, *adam19* (early) and *shisa3*, *frdm6* (late) for the cranial branch, and *mafb*, *klb*, *mdk* (early) and
285 *prdm1*, *cf1*, *hoxd3* (late) for the vagal branch (Fig. 5A-B; Fig.S5). By their high specificity and early
286 expression, *nrp2* and *mafb* seemed the best early predictors of branching between the cranial and vagal
287 populations (Fig. 2E). These results match *in vivo* analyses on expression of key NC regulators, such as
288 Mafb during cardiac NC specification or Alk in cranial NC migration (38, 39) and support the validity of
289 this modelling.

290 ***Vagal to enteric split and cranial subdivisions at neural fold stages.***

291 From the apparently homogeneous clusters c7 and c9, branching analysis predicted candidates
292 regulating subsequent bifurcation. The vagal c9 seems to split into cardiac c12 and enteric nervous system
293 progenitors (ENSp) c13. For c12, early-enriched genes were *mafb*, *mycn*, *prdm1*, *nolc1* and *eef1d*, late
294 ones being *egr2*, *hoxd3*, *epha4* and *abtb2* (Fig. 5C). For c13, early genes were *olig4* and *fbn2*. Due to its
295 significantly increased expression in later c13 cells, *pax3* was identified as a late actor, but the expression-
296 pseudotime heatmap showed that *pax3* was already expressed prior to branching in ENSp progenitors and
297 increased afterward (Fig. 2D and 5D). Therefore, we also assigned *pax3* as an early c13 gene. Later c13
298 genes consist of *tnc*, *ltbp1*, *wnt11*, and *hoxb6*. Interestingly, through CHIP-seq and depletion analyses of
299 the early TF Pax3, we found that some late genes were directly bound by Pax3 as well as affected in
300 morphants (*cfb*, *bmp5*), while others showed increased (*krt8*) or decreased (*cldn1*, *hoxb6*, *hoxa7*)
301 expression after Pax3 depletion (Fig. 6A and S6). Thus, using RNA-seq after a TF’s depletion and CHIP-
302 seq data produced *in vivo* for a given TF allows a first level of validation of the branch-specific candidate
303 signatures modelled by scFates.

304 Similar analysis on cranial NC clusters (c7, c10 and c11) showed that c10-specific early genes
305 were *rpe65*, *dmbx1*, *rgr*, *lmx1a* and *zfhx4*, while late gene included *alx1* and *bmper* (Fig. 5E). Interestingly,
306 *pax3* was also expressed early in the cranial bifurcation from c7 towards c10 and c11 and later and was
307 specifically enriched in *rpe65*⁺ c10. The Pax3 CHIP-seq and MO datasets revealed that *rpe65*⁺ branch-
308 specific transcripts *comt*, *slc23a2* and *rpe65* were decreased after *pax3* depletion while others, *bmper*, *f10*,
309 *sema3a*, *dmbx1*, *slc16a12* and *kif26a*, were both depleted in Pax3 morphants and bound by Pax3 *in vivo*
310 (Fig. 6A). On the other hand, *tfap2e* expression initiated before bifurcation and was enriched in *hox dlx2*⁺
311 c11 relative to c10. Using a similar strategy, we validated that TFAP2e depletion reduced the expression
312 of nine of the *hox dlx2*⁺ branch-specific genes (e.g., early gene *mef2c*, and late genes *dlx2*, *mmp14*, *vim*),

313 and that *Tfap2e* regulated and directly bound four other genes in the c11 signature (*c9*, *vim*, *mmp14* and
314 *mycn*, Fig. 6A and S6). These data suggested by an independent strategy than GRNBoost2 that TFAP2e,
315 important for NC induction, also directly regulates cranial NC EMT and migration by controlling *vim* and
316 *mmp14*. We tested this late-stage function *in vivo* using low-level depletion of TFAP2e which still allowed
317 partial NC induction and tested for migration ability of the induced cells (Figs 6, S7). Specifically, a pre-
318 EMT NC explant co-injected with low-levels of TFAP2e MO, mRNA encoding a dexamethasone-
319 inducible TFAP2e and a lineage tracer, was grafted into a wild-type control embryo prior to EMT (stage
320 17, Fig. 6B, S7). While grafted control NC cells efficiently populated the craniofacial areas, morphant NC
321 remained at the grafted site (Fig. 6C). Importantly, when TFAP2e was re-activated in morphant NC at
322 EMT stage, cell migration was partly restored, and lineage-traced cells were found along NC cranial
323 migration routes (Fig. 6C-D). As predicted, we thus validate a later role for TFAP2e in NC cell migration.
324 Last, we tested the branching predictions, looking if the early expression of Pax3 affected the choice
325 between *rpe65*⁺ c10 and *dlx2*⁺ c11. For this, we activated *pax3* expression using an inducible form at the
326 time of predicted branching (mid-neurula stage 14) and dissected NC explants to analyze them by qRT-
327 PCR at migration stage. We found that *pax3* activated expression of c10 marker *dmbx1* while it repressed
328 expression of c11 migratory markers *mmp14* and *fn1* (Fig. 6E). We did not observe significant regulation
329 for the other markers tested such as c10 *zfhx4* and c11 *twist*. This indicates that the scFates predictions
330 have pointed at Pax3, which plays a role in some of the reciprocal regulations occurring during branching
331 between two cranial cluster states (Fig. 6F).

332 In conclusion, using computational approaches we define and analyze three main bifurcation points
333 in the premigratory NC dataset: from unbiased c5 to vagal and cranial NC, from vagal NC (c9) to cardiac
334 (c12) and ENSp (c13) fates, and from early cranial (c7) to *rpe65*⁺ (c10) and *dlx2*⁺ (c11) cranial NC. For
335 each branch, we define specific gene programs, including early actors predicted to trigger specific states.
336 Lastly, we provide several validation elements which link numerous branch-specific genes and two of the
337 early regulators, Pax3 and TFAP2e. Importantly, these analyses reveal novel functions of Pax3 and
338 TFAP2e in regulating NC development, at stages later than what was previously studied. Pax3 was found
339 to regulate branch-specific genes in both ENSp and cranial NC cells, including genes in cranial Hox-
340 negative clusters while TFAP2e was shown to regulate genes involved in EMT and migration in the cranial
341 NC cells. Altogether, these results indicate that scFates branching analysis predictions identify important
342 candidate regulators for late functions in NC development, independently from their roles during earlier

343 stages (induction) and allow testing their functions in driving state choices during later NC diversification
344 *in vivo*.

345 **Coexisting neural border, ventral and dorsal ectoderm gene programs specify neural crest and**
346 **placodes.**

347 *Neural border cell signature displays enriched ventral and dorsal gene expressions which are*
348 *regulated by Pax3*

349 Next, we decided to look at earlier stages, specifically during gastrulation, when most ectodermal
350 tissues start to be specified. To unveil the molecular mechanisms that induce and distinguish NC and the
351 neighboring cranial placodes at the ectoderm during gastrulation, we gathered data for all ectoderm cells
352 from stages 11-13 and identified 10 distinct cell clusters (c'0 to c'9; Fig. 1A and 6A). The 'neural border'
353 model suggests that the NB zone is an ectodermal area located in-between *sox2*⁺ neuroepithelium (NE)
354 and *epidermal keratin*⁺ nonneural ectoderm (NNE), co-expresses *tfap2a*, *zic1* and *pax3* and gives rise to
355 both NC and placodes (Fig. 7A-7C, S8A and S10) (40–43). The early developmental dynamics of this
356 ectodermal area has not yet been described at the single-cell level in frogs (later stages described in (44))
357 and by only two studies in chick embryos (16, 45). Moreover, it remains unclear if NB cells resemble
358 adjacent progenitors or if they exhibit a specific gene signature. From the force-directed graph plot, we
359 selected cells co-expressing high levels of *tfap2a* and *zic1* as the presumptive neural border (46–48). These
360 503 cells, depicted as zone 3, did not appear as an individual cluster, rather as cells spread out amongst
361 clusters c'1, c'2, c'5 and c'6 (Fig. 7A, S8A and S10). While we observed low cell density specifically for
362 the NB zone between stages 11 and 12, we excluded a stage-related sampling issue since NE/NNE areas
363 presented normal density. Rather this could relate to a faster transcriptional transition of NB cells
364 compared to NNE cells: if early ectoderm cells transit through the NB state quickly before switching
365 towards NC or placode states, fewer cells would be captured. Alternatively, such a plot could be obtained
366 if the NB zone was highly heterogeneous and contained a mosaic of states (NB, NNE or NE).

367 We then identified a detailed signature for the *tfap2a*⁺*zic1*⁺ cells. Several transcripts were enriched
368 from stage 11: *tfap2c*, *pax3*, *sox9*, *hes1*, *gmnn* and *myc* (Fig. 7C). Most of these transcripts also formed
369 main nodes in the whole Ectoderm connectome generated with GRNBoost2 (10085 gene connections,
370 Table S5). We examined whether Pax3, previously shown to appear as early as stage 10.5 *in vivo* (46),
371 triggers expression of NB zone signature genes *in vivo*; in Pax3 morphant NB transcriptome, we found

372 decreased expression of the other NB genes *sox9*, *axin2*, *zic3* and *zic1*, while early NE and NNE marker
373 *lhx5.1* was increased (Fig. S8B-C). These results identify a novel gene signature enriched in *tfap2a⁺zic1⁺*
374 NB cells, consolidate Pax3 as a major regulator of NB formation, and importantly, as an activator of the
375 new NB signature.

376 ***The NB zone contributes to NC and PC in parallel to convergent contributions from neural***
377 ***plate and non-neural ectoderm progenitors.***

378 Based on the force-directed graph, we hypothesized three possible developmental routes leading
379 to NC and placodes from stage 11 ectoderm cells: a) NE → NC; b) NB zone → PC and NC; c) NNE →
380 PC (Fig. 7D); these possibilities are consistent with current models of NC and PC formation, the "neural
381 border zone model" (route b) and the "neural vs non-neural" model (routes a & c) (12, 19, 40, 41).
382 Interestingly using branching analysis, no direct route was found between early NNE (*nnel1*) and NC, or
383 between NE and PC, confirming biological features, such as the partial neuralization needed for NC
384 induction or the close relationship between placodes and NNE (20, 42, 49). We applied branching analysis
385 to each potential route and compared the resulting gene programs underlying NC vs PC fate decisions.
386 For route (a), branching towards NP from the NE state involved early genes *elav3* and *sall2* and late genes
387 *nkx6* and *tubb2b*, consistent with current knowledge on neural plate induction (*sall2*, *nkx6*) and primary
388 neurogenesis (*elav3*, *tubb2b*) (Fig. 7E) (50). Route (a) branching towards NC involved early genes *zic1*
389 and *foxd3* and late genes *c3*, *myc*, *sox8*, *sox9*, *pcdh8* and *snai2* (Fig. 7F). In comparison, NC cells emerging
390 from the NB zone by route (b) expressed *c3* and *sox9* before bifurcation, while NC markers *foxd3*, *sox8*,
391 *pcdh8*, *snail2* were enriched after splitting (Fig. 7H). Similarly, we explored both proposed routes of
392 placodal development: route (b) from NB zone showed early enrichment of *tcf7l1*, *hesx1* and late for
393 *stmn1*, *pax6*, *pitx1/2* (Fig. 7G) while route (c) from NNE exhibited early enrichment of placode specifiers
394 *six1*, *otx2*, and late expression of placode markers *egflam*, *pax6*, *pitx1/2*, Fig. S8D). Last, the route (c)
395 branching for NNE formation confirmed known developmental dynamics with early enrichment for *gata2*
396 and late for ectoderm stem cell marker *tp63* and epithelial cells *cldn1* (Fig. S8E) (51). This hierarchy of
397 gene expression, some likely to respond to external signals as well, along the different branches thus opens
398 avenues to further elaborate each of the NC- and PC-GRNs.

399 ***Different gene programs can lead distinct progenitors towards a similar state.***

400 Interestingly, according to the route studied, we found that (i) distinct genes were activated to
401 obtain the same state, and that (ii) some genes were activated with different expression dynamics relative
402 to different bifurcations. For example, during the NB→NC transition (route b, Fig. 7H), *sox9* and *c3* were
403 activated early (before bifurcation) suggesting that they could play a part in the fate decision network from
404 NB progenitors. In contrast, during the NE→NC gene program (Fig. 7F) *sox9* and *c3* were late genes
405 while *foxd3* and *zic1* were expressed early. This observation suggested a new model of fate decisions in
406 the developing ectoderm, where parallel and distinct genetic programs activated in distinct ectoderm
407 progenitors may lead to a similar state.

408 Last, by branching analysis, NB zone-specific gene *pax3* was expressed prior to bifurcation in the
409 route (b), NB→NC gene program, and proposed to activate expression of late NC branch markers *sox9*,
410 *sox8*, *zic1*, *pcdh8* and *c3* (Fig. 7H). Interestingly, by GRNBoost2 analysis, the Ectoderm connectome
411 described NC genes (*snai2*, *sox8*, *cmymc*, *c3*) connected to the rest of the network through Pax3 and Sox9
412 (Fig. 7I), therefore suggesting that Sox9 might play a yet undescribed function immediately downstream
413 of Pax3 in NC induction and upstream of the other late NC-branch markers. So far, Sox9 was known to
414 be essential for NC induction, but its epistasis with Pax3 remained unknown. We tested the epistasis
415 relationships between Pax3 and Sox9 in NC induction (*snai2*, *cmymc*, *c3* expression) by combining Sox9
416 depletion or gain-of-function in the induced-neural crest assay (iNC is Pax3/Zic1-based NC induction
417 from pluripotent ectoderm cells, Fig. S8G). Early NC marker *snail2* expression starts from gastrula stage
418 12.5 both *in vivo* and in iNC and increases at neurula stage 14 (Fig. S8H). In this experiment, Sox9
419 depletion reduced *snail2* activation as early as at stage 12.5 while co-activation of Sox9 strongly increased
420 *snail2* expression in iNC (Fig. 7J-K, S8H-I), indicating that Sox9 is required for efficient NC induction
421 by Pax3 and Zic1. Similar results were observed on *cmymc* and *c3* activation when Sox9 was depleted (Fig.
422 S7J, S9). Interestingly, when iNC explants were analyzed prior to the normal onset of *snail2* expression,
423 at mid-gastrula stage 11/11.5, Sox9 activation led to premature *snail2* expression (Fig. 7K), suggesting
424 that Sox9 synergizes with Pax3 and Zic1 at the onset of NC induction, and may act earlier than previously
425 observed (52–54).

426 In conclusion, we have defined a new transcriptional signature for the incompletely described
427 Neural Border zone, established a global Ectoderm connectome and experimentally validated NC-related
428 nodes, in particular highlighting how Sox9 enhances NC induction immediately downstream of Pax3 and
429 Zic1. We characterized three different transcriptional programs branching from neural, neural border and

430 non-neural ectoderm progenitors towards NC and PC and propose a model in which multiple co-existing
431 paths lead to the early NC or placode states in gastrula-stage ectoderm.

432 **Discussion**

433 In this work, we exploit the resolution of high-density single cell transcriptomes collected from 8
434 frog developmental stages to unravel the emergence of the neural crest lineage from the ectoderm during
435 gastrulation, followed by diversification of neural crest progenitors during neurulation, and upon EMT.
436 Modeling gene transcription dynamics around each cell state allows the inference of the underlying
437 molecular networks. We selected several important nodes for large-scale and *in vivo* experimental
438 validation (Fig. 8A and B). This study highlights the previously unknown temporal sequence of states in
439 premigratory neural crest development. Firstly, we characterize neural crest activation either from a
440 transient neural border state, or from a neural plate state during mid-gastrulation, and suggest a model that
441 reconciles current debates upon multiple possible routes leading from immature ectoderm to neural crest
442 and placodes (Fig. 8C). Secondly, we delineate the early and later neural crest transcriptome trajectories
443 during neurulation and define key regulators of branching, leading to eight transitional states and eight
444 early migration states (Fig. 8D).

445 *A reconciliatory "Model of Dual Convergence" describes the converging trajectories initiating*
446 *neural crest and placode states.*

447 The molecular signature of the neural border ectoderm has been overtly simple, with only Pax3 (in
448 frog and fish) or Pax7 (in chick) as relatively specific markers for this domain during gastrulation and
449 early neurulation stages (9, 17). Here, we have characterized the neural border ectoderm state by two
450 features: lower expression of genes expressed by adjacent neural (dorsal) and non-neural (ventral) cells
451 (*sox2*, *lhx2*, *sall2*, *gata2*, *ker19*) and increased expression of a large gene list including *zic1*, *tfap2a/c*,
452 *pax3*, *sox9*, *hes1*, *cmyc*. We find that this state seems more transient than other ectoderm states, suggesting
453 that these fate decisions occur quickly. In frog embryos, the end of gastrulation is clearly defined by
454 blastopore closure and allows more precise exploration of timing, compared to organisms with
455 simultaneous gastrulation and neurulation such as chick embryos. In frog, fate choices in the dorsal
456 ectoderm happen during the second half of gastrulation (between stage 11 and 12.5). As the neural plate
457 forms and the blastopore closes (stage 13), fate decisions are clearly established between neural, non-
458 neural, placode and neural crest with robust molecular signatures (Fig. 7C). Modeling neural crest

459 emergence from the neural border cell state confirmed the central role for Pax3 and suggested novel
460 epistatic relationships and functional synergy between Pax3 and Sox9 upstream of the definitive neural
461 crest state, defined by *snail2* expression. Importantly, we propose a novel model for the transcriptional
462 pattern of decisions between the four main ectoderm fates, neural, non-neural, placodal, neural crest.
463 Instead of the contrasting “neural border” and “non-neural vs neural” hypotheses, we find that these routes
464 may not be exclusive and find potential trajectories supporting the emergence of neural crest from either
465 the neural border or the nascent neural ectoderm on one hand, as well as two putative trajectories leading
466 to placodes from either the neural border or the non-neural ectoderm. In each case, the candidate gene
467 programs underlying those alternative trajectories involve a subset of common genes and a few specific
468 factors (Fig. 7F). For example, specific expression of *tcf7l1* and *stmn1* is found in placodes arising from
469 NB zone, compared to the NNE route (Fig. 7J and K). For neural crest, early *sox9* expression in the NB
470 route contrasts with post-bifurcation expression in the NP route (Fig. 7H and I). Thus, our SC
471 transcriptome modeling reconciles and combines previous alternatives in a "Dual convergence Model" of
472 neural crest and placode patterning, together with specific gene signatures ripe for future lineage tracing
473 studies, functional exploration (Fig. 8C) and higher resolution analyses which may or not uncover so far
474 hidden differences between NC cells of different origins. Our model also aligns with a recent study in the
475 chick embryo neural border zone, showing that a continuous gradient of early and transitional states
476 converges on each of the four main ectoderm derivatives (NE, NNE, NC, PC) (“gradient border model”
477 by Thiery et al., (45)). Further, our branching analysis also provides candidate genes driving the possible
478 transcriptional programs. From an evolutionary perspective, the dual convergence concept suggests that
479 distinct developmental GRNs, in parallel or collaboratively, can achieve a same developmental outcome,
480 serving as a redundancy mechanism or through convergent evolution for enhanced robustness in neural
481 crest evolution.

482 ***A combination of Omics and in vivo strategies validates large sets of gene regulations driving***
483 ***the dynamics of neural crest diversification.***

484 The second outcome of our study is to define the temporal dynamics of trajectories that result into
485 eight neural crest states present upon early migration stage along the cranial and vagal axial positions (Fig.
486 8D). The first key observation is the presence of a main population of NC unbiased towards any particular
487 state, expressing markers of the immature neural crest cells, from which all the other trajectories emerge.
488 This unbiased cell trajectory is maintained during and after EMT suggesting that a very plastic, stem-like
489 NC cell population emigrates and is subjected to the signals from the microenvironment prior to fate

490 choices. The second critical observation is that, for the anterior part of the body axis considered here,
491 trajectories do not emerge in a spatially linear sequence from anterior to posterior as previously anticipated
492 in a model where NC would follow an anterior-posterior wave of maturation. Two early trajectories arise
493 from both the anterior (progenitors of posterior cranial NC - c15) and the posterior-most positions (minor
494 vagal trajectory progenitors - c3) at neural plate stage (stages 13-14) prior to neural fold elevation. This is
495 followed at mid-neurula stage (stage 15-16) by the emergence of the three other main cranial and vagal
496 trajectories leading to cranial c10 and c11, and to vagal NC c12 and c13. Together with the maintenance
497 of an immature stem-like cell population from induction to emigration, this sequence of trajectory
498 determination suggests that the main cue controlling the temporal dynamics of states hierarchy in the
499 cranial and vagal NC-GRN is not a function of the time elapsed since NC cell induction, or correlated to
500 Hox gene positional information, but rather may involve response to external signals.

501 Our temporal analysis highlights three important points deepening our understanding of NC
502 biology. Firstly, there have been long standing debates about the timing of NC fate decisions, prior or after
503 EMT from the neural tube, in a variety of animal models (55). Importantly, we did not detect distinctive
504 expression of predictive differentiation/determination fate markers before EMT. This suggested that, even
505 if some NC progenitors were biased towards a given fate prior to EMT, they did not exhibit a detectable
506 signature in our dataset. However, our observations are in agreement with several lineage tracing studies
507 showing the high multipotency of most NC cells prior to EMT (28) and the determination of NC cells
508 after EMT (26, 27). Secondly, our data support the early diversification into several distinct cell states
509 prior, during and after EMT, contrasting with the recent suggestion that upon EMT the NC progenitors
510 would regroup into a single common multipotent state (15). The high cell content of our dataset proves
511 otherwise, suggesting that this previous observation made on a smaller subset of cranial NC did not fully
512 capture the diversity of pre-migratory NC states. Lastly, temporal trajectory analysis unravels the branch-
513 specific dynamics of gene expression underlying bifurcations and state diversification. For each
514 bifurcation, we provide a list of key genes likely to control branching choices (Fig. 5 and 6). We further
515 validate these predictions in several instances, by experimental modulation of pivotal transcription factors
516 function in the premigratory neural crest (Pax3, TFAP2e), followed by *in vivo* or deep sequencing analysis.
517 In sum, our study provides a comprehensive view of the hierarchy of molecular decisions driving the
518 cranial and vagal neural crest gene regulatory network from induction at the neural border to early
519 migration, with unprecedented resolution and deep learning-aided experimental validation. We propose a
520 new "Dual Convergence Model" for neural crest and placode lineage emergence and provide a detailed

521 roadmap of the main molecular events in the premigratory and early migrating NC-GRN. Using a
522 dedicated interactive network visualization interface, any gene of interest can be queried
523 (https://github.com/Qotov/neucrest_grn). Moreover, the detailed sequence of cell states provided here will
524 prove an essential reference for monitoring induction of neural crest derivatives, for example from patient-
525 derived induced pluripotent stem cells, when reliable specification protocols preferably recapitulate the
526 steps of embryonic development.

527 **Materials and Methods**

528 **(Extended version in S. I. Part B)**

529 ***Single cell sequencing.*** Instead of collecting new materials we re-sequenced the whole-embryo
530 SC-RNA libraries for developmental stages NF11 to NF22 (56) used in (20) generating a total of 12 billion
531 reads. SC analysis used the *X.tropicalis* v.10 genome assembly, gene models v. 10.7, STAR aligner and
532 DropEst pipeline (57, 58). After filtration by counts and genes numbers (>200 genes; >300 counts), we
533 gathered a dataset of 177250 cells (NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus, GSE198494). In the cells of interest
534 (Ectoderm and NC cells), mean counts number was 1778, and mean gene number 1035. scRNA-seq
535 postprocessing was done using Scanpy (59).

536 ***Clustering.*** For each stage, we obtained independent standard dimensionality reduction with PCA,
537 computing a neighborhood graph and UMAP (60) followed by clustering, (Leiden algorithm, (21)).
538 Cluster-specific genes were defined with differential expression analysis (scanpy t-test_overestim_var)
539 Clusters the most similar to NC cells using NC signatures from (20) were selected from the whole embryo
540 dataset. The optimal level of NC subclustering was defined by increasing cluster number and checking
541 biological meaning using specific gene expression.

542 ***GRN generation.*** With time-resolved gene expression dynamics and a list of TFs, we inferred
543 genetic co-regulation and targets with GRNBoost2 (30, 31).

544 ***Principal graph generation and branching analysis.*** We generated the main tree with PAGA
545 (23), revealing cluster-cluster relationships: early stages showed the strongest connectivity. EIPiGraph
546 indicated specific branches and bifurcation points. scFates (35) defined features significantly changing
547 along the tree. Pseudotime values and differential expression analysis determined early and late branch-
548 specific features. Insufficient sequencing depth prevented use of RNA velocity.

549 ***Xenopus laevis injections, microdissections, grafting and RNA-seq on explants.*** Animal use
550 followed recommendations of the European Community (2010/63/UE) and international guidelines

551 (Authorization APAFiS#36928-2022042212033387-v1). *In vivo* injections, NB/NC dissections and
552 grafting used *X. laevis* embryos (2, 61). Knockdown experiments used previously validated antisense
553 morpholino oligonucleotides (MO) for *pax3* or *TFAP2e* (9, 33). Individual anterior NB explant (wild-type
554 or Pax3 morphant) or anterior premigratory NC (wild-type or TFAP2e-morphant) were dissected then
555 sequenced in triplicate. (RNAseq parameters in S.I Part B).

556 **Chromatin immunoprecipitation and sequencing.** ChIPseq (62, S.I. part B) was done on mid-
557 neurula stage 14 or early NC migration stage 19 embryos, injected with trace mRNA amounts (75 pg).
558 Pax3-FLAG-HA: 100 *X. laevis* embryos/condition, three biological replicates; TFAP2e-FLAG, 100 *X.*
559 *tropicalis* embryos/condition, one biological replicate, validation controls in Fig. S4C).

560 **iNC assay.** The induced neural crest assay (iNC) uses co-activation of dexamethasone-inducible
561 Pax3-GR and Zic1-GR at gastrula stage 10.5 (47, 63). iNC is here combined with Sox9 depletion or gain-
562 of-function (53) and processed by RT-qPCR (49, Table S10).

563

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716 **Legends**

717 **Figure 1. Cell selection for neural crest, ectoderm and neural border.** (A) Ectoderm (EC, stages 11-
718 13, green) and NC cells (stages 12-22, brown) were selected from a whole embryo SC transcriptome
719 dataset. (B) Well-referenced gene identify EC and NC. Dot size: number of cells expressing the gene,
720 color shade: average expression level. Neural border was defined as stage 11-13 *tfap2a*⁺, *zic1*⁺ cells. (C)
721 3D scatter plot of NC z-scores (specificity), mean gene expression (counts) and coefficient of variation
722 (CV), defining a few highly expressed pan-NC genes, compared to the whole embryo dataset.

723 **Figure 2. The premigratory neural crest displays high transcriptomic heterogeneity.** (A) Leiden
724 clustering revealed 16 distinct states (clusters) before and during EMT (developmental stages 12-22) (see
725 supplementary text) (B) Dotplot depicting the expression of the top NC-specific genes within the different
726 clusters. (C) Top 3 enriched genes for each cluster (top and bottom lines respectively), with their
727 expression in the other clusters and hierarchical clustering between clusters. (D) Expression of key cluster-
728 specific genes, including *rpe65* (cluster 10), *cyp26c1* (clusters 4/6/15), *itga4*, *dlx2* (cluster 11), *egr2*, *mafb*
729 (cluster 12), *tnc* (cluster 13), early *olig4*, *hnf1b* (cluster 3) and muscle-like NC specific *myl1* (cluster 16).
730 *Gjb1* is expressed by all clusters but is highest in cluster 2. Genes expressed broadly in NC cells define a
731 "canonical NC" signature: early *tfap2b*, *tfap2c*, *sox9*, *snai2*, and *c9*. Multipotency-related genes are present
732 mostly until mid-neurula stage (*pou5f1-1*). (D) PAGA estimates cluster connectivity where line thickness
733 increases with stronger connections.

734 **Figure 3. Characteristics of the “unbiased” NC clusters c1-c5-c14.** (A) Expression of pluripotency
735 (*cmyp*, *sox2*, *pou5f3.1*) and early unbiased NC (*tfap2b*, *c3*, *c9*, *sox9*, *pax3*, *zic1*, *tfap2c*) genes in
736 clusters c1, c5, c14, c11, c15. Each bar is a bin of 40 cells. The “stage” line indicates cells’
737 developmental stage, the “dpt-pseudotime” cell advancement along their transcriptional path. (B) Highly
738 significant differential expression of *Pou5f1-1* and *sox2* in clusters c1-c5 (early stage, high expression),
739 c14 (mid-neurula stage, moderate expression) and c11-c15 (late stage, low expression). (C) Sustained
740 expression of unbiased NC markers *tfap2b* and *cmyp* and pluripotency marker *pou5f3.1* in micro-
741 dissected NB (stage 14), NC (stages 16 - 18) and whole embryos (stage 18). AS – antisense probe, S –
742 sense probe control.

743 **Figure 4. Pax3 and TFAP2e GRNs.** (A) RNA-sequencing on microdissected NB ectoderm either wild-
744 type (wt) or following Pax3 depletion *in vivo* (Pax3 MO) identified 1179 downregulated genes (Table S6).
745 (B) Pax3 ChIP-seq analysis identified 657 candidate direct targets, among which 475 expressed in NC.

746 (C) Chromatin peaks pulled-down by Pax3-FLAG in *prtg.L*, *efna3.L* and *itga5.s* genes. (D) Venn diagram
747 compares Pax3 target genes validated by ChIP-seq, MO-RNA-seq and GRN-boost2 modeling. List of the
748 17 genes found by all three methods. (E) Similarly, 586 genes were downregulated after TFAP2e
749 depletion. (F) TFAP2e ChIP-seq found 805 candidate direct target genes, among which 642 were
750 expressed in NC, such as *mmp14*, *vim* and *adam33* (*adam13*). (G) Venn diagram compares TFAP2e
751 putative target genes validated by ChIP-seq, MO-RNA-seq and GRN-boost2 modeling, list of the 20 genes
752 found by all three methods.

753 **Figure 5. Gene programs driving NC fate trajectories.** Transcriptomes of cells subselected around a
754 chosen bifurcation point were analyzed using tree inference and pseudotime downstream analysis,
755 yielding gene programs accompanying each trajectory. Gene programs for bifurcation (A-B) of
756 premigratory unbiased cluster 5 into cluster 9 (A) and cluster 7 (B); (C-D) of migratory bipotent vagal
757 cluster 9 into clusters 12 (C) and 13 (D); (E-F) of migratory bipotent cranial cluster 7 into clusters 10 (E)
758 and 11 (F).

759 **Figure 6. Branching analyses uncover new Pax3 and TFAP2e roles in NC at mid-neurula stage.** (A)
760 NC-specific Pax3-MO-mediated RNA-seq and Pax3-ChIP-seq identify vagal (c13) or cranial (c10)
761 branch-specific genes affected by Pax3 depletion (plain) or bound by Pax3 (bold) *in vivo*. Similarly
762 TFAP2e affects cranial branch (c11) migratory signature *in vivo*. (B) Experimental paradigm to test
763 TFAP2e function in cranial NC migration. (C) While *Tfap2e* depletion abrogates grafted NC migration
764 (*gfp* staining), reactivating TFAP2e after EMT partially rescues it. (D) Quantification of NC migration as
765 the farthest NC migration distance from the dorsal boundary (red bracket in C) relative to head width
766 (dotted line). (E) To test Pax3 putative role in driving branching of cranial NC towards *rpe65*⁺ branch 10
767 and reducing *dlx2*⁺ branch 11, Pax3 was activated at mid-neurula stage 14. Branch-specific genes'
768 expression was tested at EMT/migration stage in microdissected NC: Pax3 activated branch-10 gene
769 *dmbx1*, while reducing branch-11 genes *mmp14*, *fn1*, *twist1*. (F) Model of Pax3 participation to cranial
770 NC branching. SEM, * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, **** p<0.0001.

771 **Figure 7. Gastrula-stage ectoderm branching indicates new Pax3-Sox9 epistasis during NC**
772 **induction.** (A) Ectoderm force-directed graph: clusters (top), stages (bottom). c'0 – early ectoderm, c'1 –
773 neural ectoderm, c'2 – *st11* non-neural ectoderm (NNE), c'3 – neural border, c'4 – stage 12/13 NNE, c'5 –
774 placodes (PC), c'6 – NC, c'7 – neurons, c'8 – eye primordium, c'9 – neural plate. (B) Top-3 genes for each
775 cluster. (C) Neural border-enriched gene signature (c'3). (D) Forced-directed graph-suggested paths for

776 NC and PC. **(E)** NNE1->NP program, **(F)** NE->NC program, **(G)** NB->PC program, **(H)** NB->NC
777 program, **(I)** Connectome and branching analyses suggest novel *pax3/sox9* epistasis upstream of NC
778 specifiers *snail2*, *c3*, *cmyc*. **(J)** Validation of Pax3-Sox9-NC specifiers epistasis using iNC animal cap
779 (AC) assay at stage 12.5. **(K)** Sox9 activates *snail2* precociously in iNC. **(J, K)** A: wt whole embryo, B:
780 wt AC, C: *pax3*-GR; *zic1*-GR-injected AC, D: *pax3* -GR; *zic1*-GR; *sox9* MO-injected AC, E: *pax3*-GR;
781 *zic1*-GR; *sox9*-injected AC. All conditions were normalized to C at stage 12.5. SEM, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$,
782 *** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

783 **Figure 8. Neural crest GRN and developmental transcriptome trajectories.** **(A)** Connectomes for
784 ectoderm and neural crest (https://github.com/Qotov/neucrest_grn). **(B)** Large GRNs of the major nodes
785 Pax3 and TFAP2e. **(C)** In the "dual convergence model", neural border cells present trajectories towards
786 both placodes and NC, which converge with a trajectory from neural plate towards NC and another one
787 from non-neural ectoderm towards placodes. Branching analyses suggest the top genes underlying
788 transcriptome transitions. **(D)** Transcriptomic tree of NC cell states, across late gastrulation, neurulation
789 and epithelial-mesenchymal transition, ending at early migratory stage with gene signatures supporting
790 each trajectory. Pax3 or Tfp2e expression prior to branching (in blue) prompted *in vivo* validation of their
791 role on the branch-specific signature: branch-specific genes modulated by Pax3 or TFAP2e are shown in
792 green.

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